

Balancing Between Time Budgets and Costs in Surrogate-Assisted Evolutionary Algorithms

Supplementary Material

Cedric J. Rodriguez¹[0000-0002-6136-1438],
Peter A.N. Bosman²[0000-0002-4186-6666], and
Tanja Alderliesten¹[0000-0003-4261-7511]

Leiden University Medical Center, 2300 RC Leiden, The Netherlands
`{c.j.rodriguez,t.alderliesten}@lumc.nl`
Centrum Wiskunde & Informatica, 1090 GB Amsterdam, The Netherlands
`peter.bosman@cwi.nl`

1 Results on Benchmarks

The best performing algorithms on the BBOB-BIOBJ problems 20 to 38 are visualised using a heatmap, see Figure 1 and 2.

Fig. 1. Heatmap per BBOB-BIOBJ problem (20 to 38), visualising the algorithm with the highest median hypervolume given an optimization time and function evaluation time. The white dots indicate if there is a statistical difference between the best and second-best performing algorithm.

Fig. 2. Heatmap per BBOB-BIOBJ problem (38 to 55), visualising the algorithm with the highest median hypervolume given an optimization time and function evaluation time. The white dots indicate if there is a statistical difference between the best and second-best performing algorithm.

2 Optimisation of Biomechanical Simulations

In this section, the exact methods for contouring, meshing, simulations and organ comparison are presented.

2.1 Data and Contouring

This work focuses on the deformable image registration of 3D pelvic computed tomography (CT) scans for patients undergoing external beam radiation treatment for patients with cervical cancer through the use of biomechanical simulation. The treatment planning involves acquiring two 3D CT scans: one with an empty bladder and another with a full bladder. In the CT scans, the cervix-uterus, bladder, rectum, bowel, body, and bones are contoured by a radiation therapy technologist.

2.2 Mesh generation

The process of biomechanical simulation requires careful preparation of the rest state of the patient. This rest state is typically represented by a CT scan with an empty bladder. Initially, medical images are upsampled to a uniform voxel spacing of 1 *mm* in all dimensions. This is followed by resolving any overlaps between organ contours, and subsequently uniformly shrinking all internal structures by one voxel to ensure a minimum separation of two voxels between all organs. Additionally, the internal structures are cropped along the head-feet axis to guarantee they fit within the predefined body volume.

For the creation of surface meshes, the Marching Cubes algorithm in Skimage v0.22.0 is applied with varying step sizes tailored to different anatomical structures: 20 voxels for the body, 2 for the bladder, 4 for both the cervix-uterus and rectum, 8 for the bowel, and 10 for the bones. For the bone structure, further refinement is achieved by randomly subsampling 200 nodes. These triangular surface mesh representations of the organs and bone nodes are then integrated into a unified surface mesh representation.

To convert these surface meshes into a volumetric representation, the Python implementation of Tetgen v0.6.4 is utilized with its default settings, enhanced by quality improvement options and the inclusion of up to 1000 Steiner points, to generate a tetrahedral mesh. Finally, to ensure the tetrahedral mesh aligns with the coordinate system of the full bladder, the nodes of the mesh undergo a rigid transformation. This transformation is calculated using Raystation 10B (RaySearch Laboratories, Stockholm, Sweden), aligning the bony anatomy.

2.3 Mesh transformation - biomechanical FEM simulation

In our biomechanical simulations, the transformation of the mesh is facilitated using finite element methods (FEM) in SOFA v.21.12 software with the SofaPython3 plugin. The static FEM simulation is configured with a single Newton iteration and employs specific tolerances for correction and residuals. The

absolute correction tolerance threshold is set at $1e-3$ and the relative correction tolerance threshold is similarly set at $1e-3$. Tolerances for both absolute and relative residuals are disabled, and the simulation is configured to not diverge even if the residual is increasing. The coordinates of the mesh are resolved using a SparseLDLSolver, ensuring both efficiency and accuracy in computations.

Within the tetrahedral mesh, nodes associated with bone structures are fixed to emulate anatomical rigidity. The tetrahedral elements are assigned with specific elastic properties reflecting the mechanical behaviour of various tissues. These include a bladder with a Young’s modulus of 0.0001 and a Poisson’s ratio of 0.0000, a cervix-uterus with a Young’s modulus of 0.5000 and a Poisson’s ratio of 0.4700, a rectum modelled with a Young’s modulus of 0.0100 MPa and a Poisson’s ratio of 0.4500, and a bowel with a Young’s modulus of 0.0010 MPa and a Poisson’s ratio of 0.0000, similar to [1].

To simulate deformation, a global force characterized in three orthogonal directions is uniformly applied across all mesh nodes. Additionally, individual forces are directed at each organ—bowel, bladder, rectum, and cervix-uterus—to tailor the impact on specific tissues. Surface pressures are assigned to the triangular surfaces of the bowel, bladder, and rectum, contributing to the realistic inflation and deflation of the organs.

This simulation setup involves 19 adjustable parameters, including inter-organ elasticity, orthogonal forces, and organ-specific pressures. These parameters are critical for optimizing the simulation on a patient-specific basis. The continuous simulation parameters, along with their initial ranges, are systematically listed and detailed in Table 1.

Parameter description	# of parameters	Min	Max	Unit
Body force in orthogonal directions	3	-100	100	N
Bowel force in orthogonal directions	3	-100	100	N
Bladder force in orthogonal directions	3	-100	100	N
Rectum force in orthogonal directions	3	-100	100	N
Cervix-Uterus force in orthogonal directions	3	-100	100	N
Inter-organ Young’s Modulus	1	0.00001	0.05	MPa
Bowel pressure	1	-0.002	0.002	MPa
Bladder pressure	1	0	0.01	MPa
Rectum pressure	1	-.0025	0.0025	MPa

Table 1. Continuous parameters to be optimised for the biomechanical simulations.

2.4 Organ comparison and deformation energy

Following the simulation, the tetrahedral mesh, which represents the various organ structures, undergoes deformation. To validate these deformations, we compare the contours of the deformed organs against those observed in the

full bladder CT scans. This is accomplished by generating binary label maps for both the bladder and the cervix-uterus. The degree of similarity between these binary maps is quantified using the Dice similarity coefficient (DSC). For our optimization purposes, the average DSC values for the bladder and cervix-uterus are computed. The cervix-uterus score is used because this is the region with the highest dose during treatment, and the bladder is considered because this is the organ with the largest change in volume between the two medical images. We use the function one minus average DSC for the first objective. The second objective involves calculating the deformation energy required for each tetrahedral element, based on its elasticity properties. The total deformation energy is then computed by summing these values across all elements in the mesh.

3 Results on Real-world Application

The current simulation (after parallelisation) has an average function evaluation time of 3 seconds. When we assume an optimisation time budget of 4 hours, we get the approximation fronts as depicted in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Approximation fronts for all patients.

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